

Tungro (RTV) incidence in direct seeded and transplanted rice

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We compared RTV incidence and density of RTV vector green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix* spp. in direct seeded and transplanted IR36 and TN1 rice.

In the first experiment Jul-Sep 1986 and Apr-Jun 1987, the nursery for transplanted rice was seeded 3 wk before direct seeded rice was planted. The seedling nursery was prepared near the test field. Data were taken 47 d after transplanting (DT) and seeding (DAS).

In the second experiment Nov-Jan 1986 and Aug-Oct 1987, the nursery for transplanted rice was seeded and direct seeded rice was broadcast at the same time. A small nursery was prepared in each test plot. Data were taken 66 DAS.

Seeding rate of direct seeded rice was 100 kg/ha; spacing of transplanted rice was 20 × 20 cm. Five- × five-m plots were laid out in randomized complete block design with four replications.

RTV symptoms were scored on all plants for transplanted rice and on all plants in ten 20- × 20-cm sampling units for direct seeded rice. Rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and spherical virus (RTSV) incidence were determined by the latex test in 50-100 plants/replicate samples taken in a W-pattern from transplanted rice and in 10-50 plants/sampling unit in direct seeded rice. All plants showing symptoms were tested. GLH density was determined by 10 sweeps of an insect net in each plot.

In both experiments, there were more plants with RTV symptoms and combined RTBV and RTSV incidence in transplanted rice than in direct seeded rice (see table). GLH density was also higher in transplanted rice. □

GLH density, incidence of RTV, RTBV, and RTSV in direct seeded and transplanted IR36 and TN1 rice plants.^a IRRRI, 1986-87 dry and wet seasons.

Cultural method	GLH density (no./10 sweeps)	RTV incidence (%)	Plants (%) infected with			
			RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV	
Experiment I ^b						
IR36	Direct seeded	13 ± 8	1 ± 1	1	1	2
	Transplanted	33 ± 15	23 ± 15	64	9	12
TN1	Direct seeded	7 ± 3	6 ± 2	4	3	14
	Transplanted	71 ± 26	96 ± 3	81	1	14
Experiment II ^c						
IR36	Direct seeded	6 ± 2	1 ± 1	2	2	1
	Transplanted	12 ± 3	12 ± 6	29	2	18
TN1	Direct seeded	11 ± 4	19 ± 6	9	6	16
	Transplanted	12 ± 1	80 ± 8	66	2	23

^a± Standard deviation. ^bData taken 47 d after direct seeding or transplanting. ^cData taken 66 d after direct seeding or seedbed seeding.

Rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) on rice in Madagascar

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RYMV, reported to cause severe economic damage to rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) in West Africa, has now been identified in Madagascar.

The disease was observed in Apr 1989 in some fields at Lac Alaotra, the largest contiguous rice-growing area, and in May 1989 in some fields on the Marovoay plains in the northwest. Infected varieties were Makalioka 34, Tche kouai, Boina 1329, and Tsipala.

Naturally infected plants exhibit a bright mottle with chlorotic stripes,

sterility of panicles, and stunting. Regrowth from diseased plants showed a well defined mosaic. When the virus was mechanically transmitted to Angihika, Chianan 8, and Tsipala, the same symptoms developed.

In agar-gel double-diffusion tests, virus in crude extracts from both inoculated and systemically infected leaves reacted strongly with RYMV antiserum obtained from IITA. These tests showed the isolates from Lac Alaotra and Marovoay to be serologically identical.

RYMV is known to be transmitted by Chrysomelidae beetles. *Trichispa sericea* Guérin and *Hispa gestroi* Chapman are considered the most serious insect problem of rice in Madagascar.

Investigations on the vector beetle and the virus are under way in collaboration with FOFIFA. □

Integrated pest management—insects

Stem borer (SB) incidence at different growth stages of rainfed rice

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We compared SB incidence in farmers' fields in shallow water, deepwater, very

deepwater, and flooded rainfed rice environments 1987-88. Rice varieties were Mahsuri, Chakia 59, Jalmagna, and Madhukar, respectively.

Samples of 200 stems were taken in each environment at pre-flood, early elongation, late elongation, and maturity stages. Correlation coefficients calculated for different rice environments and growth stages are

summarized in Table 1. SB populations increased with level and duration of water in all environments (Table 2). Populations also

increased from pre-flood to maturity crop stages, irrespective of environment. □

Table 1. Incidence of SB in relation to different rice environments and different growth stages at Ghagharaghat, India, 1987-88.

Rainfed rice environment	Variety	Year	SB incidence (%) at different growth stages				<i>r</i> for different growth stages ^a
			Preflood	Early elongation	Late elongation	Maturity	
Shallow water (to 50 cm water)	Mahsuri	1987	1.5	4.5	4.5	6.5	+0.939
		1988	1.5	3.5	5.5	11.5	+0.956*
Deepwater (50-100 cm)	Chakia 59	1987	2.0	5.0	8.0	5.5	+0.708
		1988	2.5	5.5	9.5	25.5	+0.911
Very deepwater (above 1 m)	Jalmagna	1987	3.0	14.0	15.0	31.5	+0.950*
		1988	4.0	8.0	15.5	44.5	+0.981*
Flood (intermittent) (3 times up to 50 cm during 1987, 4 times up to 100 cm during 1988)	Madhukar	1987	9.5	14.5	16.5	25.0	+0.969*
		1988	-	-	-	-	-
<i>r</i> for different rice environments		1987	+0.937	+0.917	+0.848	+0.802	
		1988	+0.993	+0.862	+0.802	+0.772	

= significant at the 5% level.

Table 2. Stem damage due to SB at different rainfed rice environments and growth stages at Ghagharaghat, India, 1987-88.^a

Rainfed rice Environment	Variety	Year	Damaged stems (no.)			
			Preflood	Early elongation	Late elongation	Maturity
Shallow water (to 50 cm water)	Mahsuri	1987	3	9	9	13
		1988	3	7	11	23
Deepwater (50-100 cm)	Chakia 59	1987	4	10	16	11
		1988	5	11	19	51
Very deepwater (>1 m)	Jalmagna	1987	6	28	30	63
		1988	8	16	31	89
Flooded 2-3 times (to 50 cm) ^b	Madhukar	1987	19	29	33	50

^a200 stems selected diagonally in the field from each environment and at each growth stage. ^bThe 1988 crop failed because of flash flooding for more than 1 mo at crop initiation.

***Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) Vuill. for biological control of rice hispa (RH) in Assam, India**

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During a routine search for an alternative to insecticides for control of RH *Diadisa armigera* Olivier (Coleop-

tera, Chrysomelidae), we observed the majority of the test beetles reared in cages were dying of a fungal disease. In most cases, the beetles were found stuck to rice leaves and stems.

We cultured the fungus on potato dextrose agar medium incubated at ±24 °C. Fluffy growth of the fungus was noticed 3 d after inoculation on medium; it sporulated at 7 d. The spores were single-celled, hyaline, globose (0.8-), 1-3.5 µm in diameter, with clustering of conidiogenous rachis.

A hispa adult showing infestation with *Beauveria bassiana*. Magnification 11x.

The fungus was identified as *Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) Vuillemin; its pathogenicity was confirmed through Koch's postulates.

On RH adults, white frosty fungus growth emerged first through intersegmental membranes of the thorax and abdomen (see figure). Ultimately it covered the whole body and appendages. About 90% of the beetle population tested were killed. □

Arthropod diversity in tropical rice ecosystems

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Most organisms that live in ricefields are exogenous species that colonize the rice crop when cultivation begins. The recruitment phase is followed by an interaction phase, and the species present settle into a community.

A large proportion of the individual organisms are more or less trophically interlinked and unified in their dependence on rice.

Pest management actions are often directed at the community of rice arthropods rather than at individual